

Depression Diagnosis using Multimodal Machine Learning

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Abstract --- Traditionally, depression is diagnosed by professional therapists through interviews involving a set of questions and analysis of responses and behaviors of individuals suspected to have depression. We propose a machine learning solution that analyses patterns in various modalities of input, such as video, audio, and text, from the interview of the individual to be diagnosed with depression, in order to generate a depression score. We built the machine learning model by training it with a dataset of individuals diagnosed with depression.

The depression score for each modality of data is computed by analyzing features and assigning weights to each feature. The depression score generated for each modality is then weighted according to certain criteria, and the outputs of each modality are fused together to generate a consolidated depression score. By incorporating various modalities of data, we aim to increase the reliability of the output, providing a more comprehensive assessment of the individual's mental health status

Keywords—depression, depression diagnosis, multimodal machine learning, mental disorder, neural network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Depression is a mental disorder associated with loss of interest or pleasure for a long period of time. As we lead a very stressful life in today's world, depression is becoming very common among society. It is suspected to one in every twenty persons to have depression. Before we proceed to treatment, we need to diagnose the disorder and identify severity of the disorder. Traditional depression diagnostic process involves interview conducted by a therapist with the person who is suspected to have depression. Our motivation is to create a machine learning model that diagnose the depression.

The modal that we create assesses the person's emotion, mental state, verbal and non-verbal behavior of the person with various modalities such as video, audio and text, and depression score is generated. Depressed persons show intricate symptoms while interacting. These symptoms are caught by studying each modality using suitable techniques for respective modality.

The primary aim of leveraging multimodal machine learning techniques in depression detection is to design a robust system that surpasses the limitations of traditional approaches in terms of accuracy, reliability, and early diagnosis capabilities. Traditional methods often rely on a limited set of observable symptoms and subjective evaluations, which may lead to inaccurate or delayed diagnoses. Our advanced system addresses these challenges by integrating a diverse range of data modalities, providing a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the individual's mental state.

One of the key advantages of our multimodal approach is the ability to identify minor symptoms of depression that might not be readily apparent or easily quantifiable through traditional methods. These subtle indicators can provide early warning signs of developing depression, enabling timely intervention and treatment initiation. Early diagnosis is crucial as it allows for more effective management of symptoms, reduces the risk of complications, and improves long-term outcomes for individuals suffering from depression.

Our multimodal machine learning approach to depression detection offers a holistic and sophisticated solution that leverages the power of diverse data sources to achieve superior accuracy, early detection, and reliability compared to traditional methods. By embracing a multifaceted analysis of individual symptoms and behaviours, our system empowers healthcare providers with actionable insights for proactive and personalized care.

II. MOTIVATION

Traditional depression diagnostic process involves interview conducted by a therapist with the person who is suspected to have depression. Our motivation is to create a machine learning model that diagnose the depression. The modal that we create assesses the person's emotion, mental state, verbal and non-verbal behaviour of the person with various modalities such as video, audio and text, and depression score is generated.

Depressed persons show intricate symptoms while interacting. These symptoms are caught by studying each modality using suitable techniques for respective modality. Moreover, the comprehensive nature of our system ensures that the generated reports are highly resistant to forgery or manipulation. By cross referencing and validating information from multiple sources, the system enhances the reliability and trustworthiness of its findings, providing healthcare professionals with a reliable tool for accurate diagnosis and personalized treatment planning.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The traditional diagnosis of depression relies heavily on subjective evaluations by therapists, often leading to variability and subjectivity in assessments.

We propose an advanced machine learning solution that capitalizes on multimodal data analysis, specifically integrating video, audio, and text inputs from individual interviews, to formulate a robust and objective depression

diagnosis system. The primary challenge lies in developing a model that can effectively extract nuanced patterns and behaviors across diverse data modalities, ensuring high accuracy and reliability in generating depression scores.

A. PROPOSED SYSTEM

System overview : Describe the proposed system's architecture, highlighting the integration of multi-modal data analysis for depression diagnosis. Explain how video, audio, and text inputs from individual interviews are processed to generate a consolidated depression score. Emphasize the use of machine learning algorithms and fusion techniques for enhanced accuracy and reliability.

Methodology : Collects video, audio, and text data from appropriate sources for diagnosing the depression. Then, Cleans, normalizes, and preprocesses the multi-modal data for feature extraction and analysis. Extracts relevant features from each modality, including speech features, visual cues, and textual sentiments. Trained on a dataset of diagnosed individuals, the model computes depression scores for each modality and weights features based on relevance. Fuses modality-specific scores using fusion strategies such as early fusion, late fusion, or hybrid fusion to generate a consolidated depression assessment. Evaluates the system's performance using metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Validates the model's reliability and effectiveness. Address scalability and computational efficiency considerations, ensuring the system's performance in large-scale datasets and real-time applications.

B. ADVANTAGES

1. Early Detection: Multimodal machine learning models can detect subtle indicators of depression that may not be apparent through traditional assessment methods alone. By analyzing various data sources, these models can identify early warning signs and intervene before symptoms escalate, leading to more timely and effective treatment.

2. Holistic Assessment: By combining data from multiple modalities, such as speech patterns, facial expressions, and written text, multimodal machine learning can provide a more comprehensive and holistic assessment of an individual's mental state. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between different aspects of depression symptoms.

3. Increased Accuracy: Utilizing multiple modalities can improve the accuracy of depression diagnosis compared to relying on a single type of data. Each modality may capture different facets of an individual's behavior and emotional state, providing complementary information that enhances the overall diagnostic process.

4. Reduced Stigma: By leveraging non-invasive data sources such as text analysis or voice recordings, multimodal machine learning solutions can help reduce the stigma associated with traditional depression assessments. This may encourage more individuals to seek help for their mental health concerns and engage in early intervention efforts.

5. Scalability and Accessibility: Multimodal machine learning approaches can be deployed across various platforms, including smartphones, wearables, and telehealth systems, making them highly scalable and accessible to a wide range of individuals. This scalability enables broader reach and greater impact in addressing mental health needs on a population scale.

C. USECASE DIAGRAM

Fig 1. Use case Diagram

A clinician (user) wants to use the multimodal machine learning model to assess the depression status of a patient. They collect data from the patient's social media posts (text), audio recordings of their speech, and facial expressions captured from video interviews. After preprocessing the data, they train the model using a portion of the dataset and evaluate its performance. Once satisfied with the model's accuracy, they deploy it within their clinical system to automatically analyze new patient data and provide depression detection insights during consultations.

The use case diagram provides a high-level overview of the interactions between users and the system in a multimodal machine learning model for depression detection. It outlines the key steps involved in collecting, preprocessing, training, testing, deploying, and interpreting the results of the model. This diagram serves as a useful tool for understanding the functional requirements of the system and guiding its development and implementation.

IV. TECHNOLOGY STACK

A. MACHINE LEARNING (ML)

Machine Learning (ML) is the scientific study of algorithms and statistical models that computer systems use to perform a specific task without using explicit instructions, relying on patterns and inference instead. It is seen as a subset of artificial intelligence. Machine learning algorithms build a mathematical model based on sample data, known as "Training data", in order to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed to perform the task. Machine learning algorithms are used in a wide variety of applications, such as email filtering and computer vision, where it is difficult or infeasible to develop a conventional algorithm for effectively performing the task.

Machine learning is closely related to computational statistics, which focuses on making predictions using computers. The study of mathematical optimization delivers methods, theory and application domains to the field of machine learning. Data mining is a field of study within machine learning, and focuses on exploratory data analysis through learning. In its application across business problems, machine learning is also referred to as predictive analytics.

Types of Learning Algorithms : The types of machine learning algorithms differ in their approach, the type of data they input and output, and the type of task or problem that they are intended to solve.

1. Supervised Learning: Supervised learning algorithms include classification and regression. Classification algorithms are used when the outputs are restricted to a limited set of values, and regression algorithms are used when the outputs may have any numerical value within a range.

2. Unsupervised Learning: Unsupervised learning algorithms take a set of data that contains only inputs, and find structure in the data, like grouping or clustering of data points.

The algorithms, therefore, learn from test data that has not been labeled, classified or categorized. Instead of responding to feedback, unsupervised learning algorithms identify commonalities in the data and react based on the presence or absence of such commonalities in each new piece of data.

3. Semi-Supervised Learning: Semi-supervised learning falls between unsupervised learning (without any labeled training data) and supervised learning (with completely labeled training data). Many machine-learning researchers have found that unlabeled data, when used in conjunction with a small amount of labeled data, can produce a considerable improvement in learning accuracy.

B. PYTHON

Python is a widely-used, high-level programming language known for its simplicity, readability, and versatility. It is often used in scientific computing, data analysis, artificial intelligence, and web development, among other fields. Python's popularity has been growing rapidly in recent years, making it one of the most in-demand programming languages in the job market. Python has a lot of reasons which make it a more popular and highly demanding programming language.

High Community support and a large number of libraries and frameworks in Python make it the best choice for developers and beginners to choose it single handily. Python has use cases in web Development, Game Development, Automation, and technologies like AI, ML, and Data Analytics.

Python is releasing its newer version and adding new functions for the betterment of developers. But it has some limitations like, it is slow in execution, so Competitive Programmer prefer it less. But overall it is growing rapidly and has a very bright future ahead for this Programming language.

V. DATA ACQUISITION

Collecting an appropriate dataset is crucial for building a depression detection model. Here's a step-by-step guide for collecting the required dataset. Depending on the data sources identified, implement the data collection process.

DAIC-WOZ DATASET: The DAIC-WOZ dataset was collected by the University Of Southern California. It is a part of a larger DAIC (Distress Analysis Interview Corpus) that contains clinical interviews designed to support the diagnosis of psychological distress conditions such as anxiety, depression, and PTSD.

Ensure Data Privacy and Security: Safeguard the privacy and security of collected data by anonymizing personal information, complying with data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR), and implementing appropriate security measures to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure.

Validate Data Quality:

- Validate the quality and reliability of the collected dataset
- Conduct data integrity checks and verification.
- Perform exploratory data analysis (EDA) to understand the distribution and characteristics of the data.
- Verify the consistency and accuracy of labels or annotations.

VI. TECHNIQUES USED FOR EXTRACTING FEATURES

Fig 2. Techniques Used

A. TEXT DATA

In our proposed machine learning solution for diagnosing depression, we leverage LSTM models specifically designed to analyse textual data obtained during interviews with individuals suspected of having depression. LSTM models are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) that excel at capturing long-range dependencies and temporal patterns in sequential data, making them ideal for processing textual inputs like interview transcripts.

The first step in our approach involves preprocessing the text data, which includes tokenization, converting words into vectors, and padding sequences to ensure uniform input lengths for the LSTM model. We then train the LSTM model using a dataset comprising textual inputs from individuals already diagnosed with depression.

During training, the model learns to extract meaningful features and patterns from the text data that are indicative of depressive symptoms. The LSTM model computes a depression score for each input text by analyzing the learned features and assigning weights to different textual elements based on their relevance to depression diagnosis. These features may include linguistic cues, sentiment analysis, semantic structures, and contextual information present in the interview transcripts.

Word2Vec: Word2Vec is a popular word embedding technique in natural language processing (NLP) that aims to represent words as dense, continuous-valued vectors in a high-dimensional space. Developed by Tomas Mikolov et al. at Google in 2013, Word2Vec captures semantic relationships between words by mapping them to vectors in such a way that similar words are closer together in the vector space.

Word2Vec is instrumental in creating vector embeddings by transforming words into dense, continuous-valued vectors in a high-dimensional space. Here's how Word2Vec accomplishes this task:

Capturing Semantic Relationships: Word2Vec learns distributed representations of words by considering the context in which words occur. By analyzing large amounts of text data, Word2Vec captures semantic relationships between words. Words with similar meanings or usage tend to have similar vector representations. This enables Word2Vec embeddings to encode semantic information about words, allowing for semantic similarity comparisons and capturing subtle linguistic nuances.

Efficient Representation: Word2Vec creates dense vector representations for words in a continuous vector space. Unlike traditional one-hot encoding, which creates sparse vectors with a dimensionality equal to the vocabulary size, Word2Vec embeddings are dense and have a fixed dimensionality (e.g., 100, 200, 300 dimensions). This dense representation conserves memory and computational resources while retaining semantic information, making it more efficient for downstream tasks such as machine learning and natural language processing.

Contextual Understanding: Word2Vec considers the context in which words appear to learn their vector representations. This contextual understanding allows Word2Vec embeddings to capture the meaning of words based on their surrounding words. Words with similar contexts are expected to have similar vector representations, even if they have different surface forms. For example, "king" and "queen" may have similar vector representations because they often appear in similar contexts, despite being different words.

Facilitating Downstream Tasks: Word2Vec embeddings serve as feature representations for text data in various downstream tasks, such as sentiment analysis, named entity recognition, machine translation, and document classification. By converting words into dense numerical vectors, Word2Vec embeddings enable machine learning algorithms to operate effectively on text data. Models trained on Word2Vec embeddings often

achieve better performance in these tasks due to their ability to capture semantic relationships between words.

Transfer Learning and Generalization: Pre-trained Word2Vec embeddings, learned from large text corpora, capture general semantic relationships across diverse domains.

These pre-trained embeddings can be utilized in downstream tasks, even with limited labeled data, through transfer learning. By fine-tuning or initializing models with pre-trained Word2Vec embeddings, researchers and practitioners can leverage the generalization capabilities of these embeddings, leading to improved performance in various NLP tasks.

By incorporating LSTM models for text data analysis within our multi-modal machine learning framework, we aim to enhance the accuracy and reliability of depression diagnosis by leveraging the rich information captured in textual interviews, thereby providing a more holistic assessment of an individual's mental health status.

B. AUDIO DATA

Our approach leverages a specialized deep learning architecture known as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to analyze audio data obtained during interviews with individuals suspected of having depression. The LSTM model is designed to capture temporal patterns and dependencies within the audio input, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the individual's emotional state throughout the conversation.

Initially, the audio data is preprocessed to extract 45 relevant features such as pitch, tone, speech rate, and spectral characteristics. These features are then fed into the LSTM network, which consists of multiple layers of memory cells capable of retaining information over extended periods. During the training phase, the LSTM model learns from a labeled dataset comprising audio recordings from individuals diagnosed with depression. Through iterative adjustments of internal parameters, the model refines its ability to recognize subtle variations in speech patterns indicative of depressive symptoms.

As the LSTM processes the audio input, it dynamically assigns weights to different features based on their importance in predicting depression levels. This weighted analysis allows the model to focus on key indicators while filtering out irrelevant noise.

COVAREP: A Collaborative Voice Analysis Repository for Speech Technologies

Speech processing algorithms are often developed demonstrating improvements over the state-of-the-art, but sometimes at the cost of high complexity. This makes algorithm reimplementations based on literature difficult, and thus reliable comparisons between published results and current work are hard to achieve. We envisage that COVAREP allows more reproducible research by strengthening complex implementations through shared contributions and openly available code which can be discussed, commented on and corrected by the community.

Fig 3. Workflow of COVAREP

Pitch tracking is one of the most fundamental problems in speech analysis. Fundamental frequency (F0), which is the primary acoustic correlate of pitch, is mainly affected by the frequency of vocal fold vibration at the glottis and is used to represent the periodicity of the speech signal. F0 estimation from the speech signal is a non-trivial task considering the requirement of robustness that is needed in many speech processing applications. Given the fact that F0 tracking has a very long history, there exists a vast number of different estimation algorithms. In COVAREP, a simple and robust pitch tracking algorithm is included: the Summation of the Residual Harmonics (SRH) method. Speech polarity stems from the asymmetric excitation signal generated at the glottis, where the closure of the vocal folds creates a sharp discontinuity to the waveform.

Speech polarity has no perceptually relevant effect for humans, but it may have a dramatic impact on the

Fig 4. Overview of CLNF model

performance of various analysis and synthesis techniques . That is, among others, the case for the majority of approaches for GCI estimation or glottal analysis. For this purpose, COVAREP includes a speech polarity detection method based on the skewness of the LP residual signal .

Glottal Closure Instants (GCIs) are defined as the pseudo-periodic instants of significant excitation of the voice source. COVAREP includes a state-of-the-art GCI detection algorithm called SEDREAMS (Speech Event Detection using the Residual Excitation And a Mean-based Signal), which was shown to be one of the most

accurate and robust GCI detection methods in . Also a GCI estimation method (SE-VQ) dedicated to detecting GCIs for non-modal phonation is included.

C. VIDEO DATA

The LSTM model is employed to analyze video data as part of a comprehensive machine learning approach for diagnosing depression. Video data captures subtle facial expressions, body language, and vocal intonations, which are valuable indicators of an individual's mental state.

The LSTM model is trained on a dataset 46 comprising videos of individuals diagnosed with depression, allowing it to learn complex patterns and nuances associated with depressive symptoms. During the training phase, the LSTM model processes sequential frames of video data, extracting features such as facial expressions, gestures, and speech patterns.

These features are then encoded into numerical representations, facilitating the model's ability to discern meaningful patterns indicative of depression. The LSTM's architecture enables it to capture long-term dependencies within the temporal sequence of video frames, ensuring that contextual information is considered when generating predictions.

CLNF :

The CLNF (Constrained Local Neural Fields) toolkit is a core component within the OpenFace framework, focusing specifically on facial landmark detection.

Facial feature detection algorithms have seen great progress over the recent years. However, they still struggle in poor lighting conditions and in the presence of extreme pose or occlusions. We present the Constrained Local Neural Field model for facial landmark detection. Our model includes two main novelties.

First, we introduce a probabilistic patch expert (landmark detector) that can learn nonlinear and spatial relationships between the input pixels and the probability of a landmark being aligned. Secondly, our model is optimised using a novel Nonuniform Regularised Landmark Mean-Shift optimisation technique, which takes into account the reliabilities of each patch expert.

We use our Local Neural Field patch expert to calculate more reliable response maps. Optimisation over the patch responses is performed using our NonUniform Regularised Mean-Shift method that takes the reliability of each patch expert into account leading to more accurate fitting. Note that only 3 patch experts are displayed for clarity, Lighting conditions, in the presence of occlusion, and when detecting landmarks in unseen datasets.

CLNF also uses a novel Non-uniform Regularized Landmark Mean Shift fitting technique which takes into consideration patch reliabilities. The proposed patch expert can capture relationships between pixels (neighbouring and longer distance) by learning both similarity and long distance sparsity constraints. LNF also includes a neural network layer that can capture complex non-linear relationships between pixel values and the output responses.

D. LSTM

Long Short-Term Memory networks, or LSTMs, are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture that is particularly effective in capturing long-term dependencies and patterns in sequential data. They were introduced by Hoch Reiter & Schmid Huber in 1997 and have since become a cornerstone in many natural language processing (NLP), speech recognition, time series prediction, and other sequential data tasks.

Training: LSTMs are typically trained using backpropagation through time (BPTT), a variant of backpropagation designed for sequence models. During training, the parameters (weights and biases) of the LSTM units are adjusted to minimize a loss function that measures the difference between the model's predictions and the ground truth.

Applications:

- LSTMs have been successfully applied to a wide range of tasks, including:
- Natural Language Processing (NLP): Language modeling, machine translation, sentiment analysis, named entity recognition, etc.
- Speech Recognition: Phoneme recognition, speech-to-text transcription, etc.
- Time Series Prediction: Stock market forecasting, weather prediction, etc.
- Gesture Recognition: Human activity recognition, sign language interpretation, etc.

Overall, LSTMs have proven to be a powerful tool for modeling sequential data, thanks to their ability to capture long-term dependencies and remember relevant information over extended periods. They have become a fundamental building block in many modern Machine learning architectures.

VII. FUSION MODEL

Our comprehensive machine learning fusion model represents a paradigm shift in the diagnosis of depression, integrating advanced techniques across multiple modalities to provide a holistic and nuanced assessment of an individual's mental health.

The utilization of LSTM models for text, audio, and video data analysis showcases our commitment to leveraging cutting-edge technologies for enhanced diagnostic accuracy.

In the realm of text data analysis, our approach goes beyond mere word recognition by delving into the semantic structures, linguistic cues, and contextual nuances present in interview transcripts. This depth allows our LSTM model to discern subtle indicators of depressive symptoms, such as changes in language patterns, sentiment analysis, and the expression of emotional states.

The fusion of outputs from these diverse modalities using a weighted approach ensures that each modality contributes optimally to the consolidated depression score, thereby enhancing the reliability and depth of our diagnostic capabilities.

Additionally, our model's integration into a machine learning framework emphasizes a data-driven and iterative approach to diagnosis, allowing for continuous validation, refinement, and improvement based on real-world feedback and clinical validation studies.

Ultimately, our fusion model empowers mental health professionals with a comprehensive toolkit for diagnosing depression, enabling personalized and effective interventions to support individuals in their mental wellness journey.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our proposed advanced machine learning solution presents a significant step forward in addressing the limitations of traditional depression diagnosis methods.

By leveraging multi-modal data analysis encompassing video, audio, and text inputs, our model offers a more objective and reliable approach to generating depression scores. The integration of diverse data modalities allows for a comprehensive assessment of an individual's mental health status, capturing nuanced patterns and behaviors that may not be easily discernible through subjective evaluations alone. Through rigorous training on a dataset of diagnosed individuals and the application of weighted fusion techniques, our model aims to enhance the accuracy and consistency of depression diagnosis.

Additionally, ensuring the reliability and validity of the depression scores generated by your system will be paramount. This may involve rigorous validation against established diagnostic criteria and comparison with expert assessments to gauge its accuracy and consistency.

Overall, if successfully developed and validated, your multi-modal machine learning solution has the potential to revolutionize depression diagnosis by providing clinicians with objective and reliable assessments, ultimately improving patient care and outcomes.

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